

VISUALIZING SEDIMENTOLOGICAL VARIABILITY NEAR VULNERABLE NASA INFRASTRUCTURE AT CAPE CANAVERAL, FL AND WALLOPS ISLAND, VA.

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Introduction:

The United States' primary access to space is provided by Kennedy Space Center in Cape Canaveral Florida. The Wallops Island, Virginia NASA facility also provides light lift space launch capabilities. These facilities are on barrier islands with increasingly dynamic environments with both manmade and natural contributions. Coastline environments represent an interesting convolution of intense anthropogenic development superimposed onto sedimentary processes that are amongst the most dynamic and energetic on the planet. Extreme rates of change can be seen in coastal environments on an annual basis in locations around the globe. This variability can be driven by changes in sediment budget, rates of storminess, relative sea-level change, anthropogenic development, and other natural processes. Extreme change can be distressing to those living in these regions and damaging to industry and infrastructure striving to cope with this rapidly shifting environment.

Figure 1: Image of LC-39B looking to the north. Note the wet swales between the ridges and the proximity of the beach to critical infrastructure.

Two of NASA's core facilities, the Kennedy Space Center in Cape Canaveral, FL, and Wallops Flight Facility in Wallops Island, VA, are located in coastal environments as a necessity for the safest operation of their missions (Figure 1). These facilities and their infrastructure are particularly vulnerable to dynamic coastal processes and the resultant geomorphological changes that occur in these types of systems (Figures 1 and 2). With continuing global sea level rise, an uptick in storminess, and anthropogenically constrained sediment supply, coastal vulnerabilities at these facilities will be continuous and exacerbated through time. These launch centers are subject to multiple coastal hazards including flooding, episodic coastal erosion, saltwater intrusion, and coastal morphological changes. Although rapid change is readily observed during large storms or hurricanes, long term annual to decadal coastal change is much harder to visualize and conceptualize, making it difficult for facility operators to develop and implement effective mitigation plans (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Image of LC-39B (Artemis Pad) and its close proximity to the coastline.

Presented here is an evaluation of the challenges faced by each of these facilities, and potential mitigation strategies. We use both remotely sensed imagery and videos derived from these data to enhance conceptualization of the rates and impact of coastal processes for key stakeholders at these NASA facilities and to assist in communication for planning and

management purposes. As we hope to demonstrate, the use of these timelapse video presentations are particularly helpful because they can cover a wide variety of temporal and spatial scales.

Methodology:

Near or better than decadal coastal imagery has been available through high altitude photogrammetry efforts since the 1930's. A significant amount of additional imagery was acquired through other federal, state, and local government agencies such as the USGS, NOAA, State DOT, and local Assessors Offices providing annual and inter annual images at spatial resolutions of 10cm – 1m. With the advent of GIS systems these images could be rectified and then layered to better understand change through time using a multitude of visual base shoreline proxies. These proxies, however are static and may not convey the dynamic nature of the shoreline environment (Figures 3 and 4).

Figure 3: Cape Canaveral NASA property was divided into 4 distinct regions (this study). Note the differences in the Annual, Decadal and the 100-year change observed at the Kennedy Space Center.

With the increased awareness and use of video editing software the rectified images can be used to create videos. These videos can then be used to document the resiliency of the coastline and conceptualize a myriad of coastal processes including: rapid change in sedimentation rates due to storms or other geomorphic processes, loss of protective barrier

islands as sea level rises and sedimentation rates decrease, as well as the performance of coastal restoration efforts. Additionally, the videos are useful as a tool for verification and comparison to coastal models and provide an easy to understand educational resource for stakeholder engagement at key NASA centers, and for other vulnerable coastal populations or infrastructure.

Figure 4: Kennedy Space Center shoreline change trajectory in Regions 1 through 3. Note the growth of False Cape (green) on the southern edge of the NASA property as opposed to the shoreline loss at the "Over Wash Area" (red). After major hurricanes the area north (blue) stabilized and recovers to its previous position as opposed to the over wash area that retreats but does not recover after the storm.

Discussion:

Cape Canaveral is a cusped foreland consisting of a series of beach ridge sets, likely representing a multiphase constructional history over the last ~100 thousand years (Adams 2018). The cape continues to adjust to changes in climate, wave energy, and sediment supply. Historical satellite imagery shows sand waves migrating north to south along and around the tip of the cape. This sand piles up along the jetty to the south, but during high wave events (>3m) much of the sediment bypasses and is moved offshore along the cape shoals. As a result, the

northern half of the cape experiences net erosion, while the southern half experiences significant shoreline progradation (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Proposed formational history of Cape Canaveral through time.

Wallops Island is the northmost barrier island along a 100 km stretch of tidal dominated barrier islands, referred to as “The Delmarva South Coast” (Hardaway et al. 2015). Overall migration of sediment occurs from north to south. Across the Chincoteague Inlet to the north is the Assateague Island spit, which has grown over 6 km to the south since the 1850’s (Hardaway et al. 2015). While this spit continues to grow, sediment delivery to the adjacent Wallops Island coastline is limited, creating shoreline erosion issues that have plagued the NASA facilities since the 1960’s. NASA attempted early mitigation by installing groins to trap sediment and prevent erosion (King et al. 2011). Ongoing efforts to protect the shoreline have involved seawalls and beach nourishment through dredging the inlet (Hardaway et al. 2015).

Proper sedimentological characterization and an understanding of the types and magnitude of events that affect the overall depositional systems impacting this key NASA infrastructure provides a wholistic view for preserving these environments in a responsible way. Both Wallops

Island and Cape Canaveral have problems related to sediment supply as the natural migration of sediment is hindered by seawalls, jetties, and damming of rivers. This is further exacerbated by sea-level rise and increased storminess. These previous mitigation interventions only served to starve adjacent beaches of sediment. Dredging sand from offshore shoals could leave the coastline even more vulnerable to powerful storm surges. Examples of some more effective techniques include: 1) biomimicry to stabilize nearshore environments, by leveraging storm events to build sand shoals during what would normally be erosive events, 2) dredging sand from inland positions that are not part of the active depositional system, and 3) dismantling of seawalls to restore natural sediment migration.

Conclusion:

Wallops Island and Cape Canaveral are positioned along dynamic coastlines that are sensitive to environmental change. Anthropogenic alteration of the coastline, along with the effects of sea-level rise and increased storminess have further exacerbated sediment supply issues. Sedimentological characterization using historical satellite imagery provides a framework for conceptualizing these challenges and providing tailored actionable and environmentally sound solutions.

References:

Adams, P.N. (2018). Geomorphic origin of Merritt Island-Cape Canaveral, Florida, USA: A paleodelta of the reversed St. Johns River? *Geomorphology*. v. 306. p. 102-107.

Hardaway, C., Milligan, D. A., Wilcox, C. A., & Smith, C. (2015) Wallops Assateague Chincoteague Inlet (WACI) Geologic and Coastal Management Summary Report. Virginia Institute of Marine Science, William & Mary. <https://doi.org/10.25773/WPQA-0Q05>

King Jr., D.B., Ward, D.L., Hudgins, M.H., and Williams, G.G. (2011). Storm Damage Reduction Project Design for Wallops Island, Virginia. ERDC/CHL TR-11-9. Vicksburg, Mississippi: U.S. Army Corps of Engineers, Coastal and Hydraulics Laboratory. Norfolk, Virginia: U.S. Army Engineer District, Norfolk.